

The Importance of Correct Organization of the Nutrition Regime of Football Players in Sports Clubs

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Abstract:

Modern sports achievements are based on the principles of optimal nutrition, no less than the characteristics of neuropsychic and muscle activity during training. This scientific article is devoted to the analysis of the diet and water-drinking regime of athletes engaged in sports. Sports games are characterized by alternating loads of different intensity with periods of rest. The mechanism of providing energy to muscle work is based on a mixed, i.e., anaerobic-aerobic process. The result in the game depends on the level of development of the neuromuscular apparatus, cardiovascular and respiratory systems, visual analyzer, and is determined by the perfection of technical and tactical skills. There can be large individual differences in energy expenditure in athletes, which depends on many factors that affect the intensity of physical activity during the game. For this reason, the energy content of the diet can be very variable. The qualitative and quantitative distribution of food and liquid consumption in the daily diet of team sports athletes should be carried out taking into account the upcoming game. The article provides a literary analysis of the influence of nutrients on the recovery of sports performance of sports athletes.

Keywords: types of sports, water-drinking regime, nutrition of athletes, energy value of food, physical load

INTRODUCTION

A healthy diet is important for any person, but especially for an athlete, a football game is a long-lasting physical load, so high demands should be placed on his diet. "Food is fuel for an athlete," said Pele, the king of football. It is impossible not to agree with this opinion, because the

performance of a football player during training and games depends more on his proper nutrition. Therefore, reaching the peak of modern football means not only playing well, but also eating well.

On the back of any food package there will be a small table that says "Nutrition Value". It will show the energy values, as well as fats, proteins, carbohydrates, minerals and drugs (vitamins) contained in this product. Why does a football player need to know these things? If he doesn't have enough energy for his last jump, if he gets home from practice and falls asleep before he can eat, then it's time to focus on this schedule. A football player who gets acquainted with the information of this table, pays attention to it and eats, will be the fastest, most fit and able to work during training.

Thus, a balanced meal for a football player should not only be tasty and useful, but the most important for an athlete should meet two important requirements: in terms of quality, the food should have all nutrients (fats, proteins, carbohydrates, minerals, salts and vitamins). and, in terms of quantity, should cover all the body's energy expenditure (in kilocalories).

Energy consumption depends on the individual characteristics of the player (age, weight, height) and, most importantly, on the nature of the loads. During training, an athlete should consume an average of 65-75 kilocalories of energy per kilogram of body weight per day through food. Based on this, the amount of energy that the athlete should take in a day is calculated.

The daily routine of eating should always be consistent with the general sports regime. The times of breakfast, lunch, afternoon and dinner should always be the same - this is the main condition for good digestion of food products. It is impossible to practice and play on an empty stomach. The most effective for a football player is to eat four or five times a day. In separate meals (razdelnoye pitaniye), carbohydrate, fat, and protein foods are not mixed in one sitting. For example, it is impossible to eat fruits or sweets immediately after a protein meal. Fruits or sweets can be eaten after 2 hours. Only foods with the same nutrient content should be eaten at each meal.

The diet directly depends on the football player's stage of preparation, training loads. For example, during preparation, i.e., when athletes go to a training session to improve their general physical fitness, they eat protein-rich foods (meat, fish, eggs, etc.) necessary for muscle development, and carbohydrates and vitamins (oats, buckwheat) to improve endurance. by eating porridges, vegetables and fruits) should be enriched by eating foods rich in To develop the qualities of speed and strength, a football player needs products rich in phosphorus and calcium (cheese, fish, etc.). The meal taken before the match (at least 3 hours before the start of the match) should be high-calorie, low-volume, rich in proteins and carbohydrates (but not fatty). Because these provide 60-65% of energy to a football player, 15% of food is proteins, and the rest are fats. The idea that an athlete should eat as much as possible before a game is wrong. It is not the quantity of food that matters here, but the quality of its nutrients. At this time, the following diet is recommended: steamed meat, poultry dishes with vegetable garnish, seafood dishes, rice and oatmeal porridge, eggs, yogurt, fruit and vegetable juices, vitamin compotes.

Before training, especially responsible games, it is not advisable to eat hard-to-digest foods with fatty products (beef fat, fried meat, beans, buckwheat, semech, etc.). In addition, on the day of the main game, you should drink more fluids, because the body should not be dehydrated during the game. In this case, you need to follow the diet, not only before the game, but every day.

After sports loads, food should be rich in enough protein and nutritious. Products rich in fiber can be used - they help to restore vitamins and mineral salts used during exercise and games. Fish dishes, dairy products, vegetables and fruits are the best for these purposes.

ADVICE FOR FOOTBALL PLAYERS ON NUTRITION

It's best to eat as many carbohydrate-rich foods as possible two to three days before the game. It serves to increase glycogen and glucose reserves in the body and maintain energy during the game.

It is better to eat 3-4 hours before going to the game, that is, the stomach should digest the food. It is better not to eat as much as possible close to the game. After the game, about 2-3 hours later, it is necessary to eat foods rich in carbohydrates, because a lot of energy is spent during the game.

From drinks, mostly isotonic waters are good or, if not, natural juices are also useful. Eat a balanced diet whenever possible. It goes without saying that alcohol is absolutely unnecessary. Drinking milk in the morning is also beneficial.

In conclusion, it should be said that proper nutrition plays an important role for the player's body. Food also promotes growth, rewarming the body, and healing injuries. In order to play football hard, you need to know how to maintain a healthy diet that includes many nutrients that give the body good energy.

Proper nutrition for athletes.

Many athletes believe that there is nothing shameful about pre-competition fries and clutches, but their favorites and eighth places attract them. However, in the opinion of such an athlete, his body needs to be solved using some resources before being assigned completely different tasks for the majority of people around him.

Our food is our resources. Therefore, proper sports nutrition should be different from the menu of non-athletes.

Calorie control of sports nutrition.

Food calories should fully cover daily energy expenditure. If the amount of food is less than the energy expenditure, the energy balance is negative. If this situation lasts for several days or weeks, the athlete will lose weight.

A simple way to control the body's energy expenditure with the amount of food (calories) is to regularly determine body weight on a scale.

Maintaining the same body weight indicates that nutrition, that is, the amount of food, is in moderation.

The increase in body weight due to the thickening of the subcutaneous adipose tissue, while the development of muscles is not very significant, shows that the amount of food is high, and energy consumption is low.

On the other hand, a gradual decrease in body weight, without any signs of illness, indicates a lack of food, or the amount of food consumed covers the body's energy consumption.

It should also be noted that a young athlete who has just started training may lose up to 3 kg of body weight in a few days and weeks due to excessive exertion, excessive energy expenditure, loss of water due to the reduction of the subcutaneous fat layer and excessive sweating. may decrease.

As the athlete's training increases, his movements during training sessions are regular, he does not make unnecessary movements, so his body weight remains constant or, due to the better development of his muscles, his body weight may increase to a certain extent.

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